

Implementation of a Nurse-Driven Ventilator Weaning Protocol at a Community Hospital

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Background

Mechanical Ventilation

- Improves gas exchange in patients with compromised breathing.
- Provides oxygen to the patient while decreasing patient's work of breathing
- Life supporting measure, but costly, and carries potential risk for complications

Prolonged Mechanical Ventilation

- Risk for ventilator lung injuries: pneumonia, barotrauma, death
- Increase hospital costs

Nurse-Driven Ventilator Weaning Protocol (NDVWP)

- Structured guide to discontinue mechanical ventilation
- Can effectively wean patients off the ventilator faster than physician led weaning
- Assesses patient readiness to wean off vent

Purpose Statement

- The purpose of this DNP project is to educate and train nursing staff on a NDVWP for hospital implementation

Methods

Pre and Post evaluation design

- Pretest will be used to assess nurse baseline knowledge of ventilator weaning
- Nurses will receive standardized education on training
- Post test will be conducted to assess nurse comprehension of learned material
- NDVWP will be implemented in the ICU.

Framework

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at
What the Facilitator Does

Burn's Wean Assessment Checklist

Burns Wean Assessment Program checklist			
Patient _____			
Yes	No	Not assessed	General assessment
___	___	___	1. Hemodynamic status stable (pulse rate, cardiac output)?
___	___	___	2. Free from factors that increase or decrease metabolic rate (seizures, temperature, sepsis, bacteremia, hypothyroidism/hyperthyroidism)?
___	___	___	3. Hematocrit >25% (or baseline)?
___	___	___	4. Systemically hydrated (weight at or near baseline, balanced intake and output)?
___	___	___	5. Nourished (serum albumin >2.5 mg/dL, parenteral/enteral feedings maximized)? (If albumin is low and anasarca or third spacing is present, score for hydration should be no)
___	___	___	6. Electrolytes within normal limits? (including calcium, magnesium, phosphorus) Correct calcium for albumin level
___	___	___	7. Pain controlled? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	8. Adequate sleep/rest? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	9. Appropriate level of anxiety and nervousness? (subjective determination)
___	___	___	10. Absence of bowel problems (diarrhea, constipation, ileus)?
___	___	___	11. Improved general body strength/endurance (eg, out of bed in chair, progressive activity program)?
___	___	___	12. Findings on chest x-radiograph improving?
Yes	No	Not assessed	Respiratory assessment
<i>Gas flow and work of breathing</i>			
___	___	___	13. Eupneic respiratory rate and pattern (spontaneous respirations <25/min, without dyspnea, no use of accessory muscles) This item is assessed with the patient off ventilator support while parameters in items 20-23 are measured.
___	___	___	14. Absence of adventitious breath sounds (rhonchi, rales, wheezing)?
___	___	___	15. Secretions thin and minimal?
___	___	___	16. Absence of neuromuscular disease/deformity?
___	___	___	17. Absence of abdominal distention/obesity/ascites?
___	___	___	18. Oral endotracheal tube >7.5 or trach >6.5
<i>Airway clearance</i>			
___	___	___	19. Cough and swallow reflexes adequate?
<i>Strength</i>			
___	___	___	20. Negative inspiratory pressure \pm 20 cm H ₂ O
___	___	___	21. Positive expiratory pressure \pm 30 cm H ₂ O
<i>Endurance</i>			
___	___	___	22. Spontaneous tidal volume >5 mL/kg?
___	___	___	23. Vital capacity >10 to 15 mL/kg?
<i>Arterial blood gases</i>			
___	___	___	24. pH 7.30-7.45
___	___	___	25. Paco ₂ approximately 40 mm Hg (or baseline) with minute ventilation <10 L/min (evaluated while patient is on ventilator support)
___	___	___	26. Pao ₂ >60 mm Hg with fraction of inspired oxygen <40%

To score the assessment, divide the number of yes responses by 26.

Implementation Plan

- Implement NDVWP in the ICU with intubated patients
- Burns Wean assessment Program will be used to assess patient readiness for ventilator weaning
- Protocol will be piloted from 7am to 7pm. At 4 hour intervals and PRN.
- Sum of data will be collected at the end of each month.
- Data will be compared to pre protocol data.

Anticipated Results

- Decrease time on mechanical ventilation through early assessment of patient's readiness to wean from ventilator
- Decrease hospital costs
- Decrease incidence of ventilator associated complications
- Improve nurse workflow with ventilated patients

Discussion

- NDVWPs can mitigate inconsistency with ventilator weaning
- NDVWP has the potential to decrease adverse events associated with mechanical ventilation (e.g., pulmonary infections, lung trauma, mortality)
- Given the benefits of NDVWPs, they are a suggested method to wean patients off the ventilator in institutions that do not have a weaning protocol